

Studies on 2-Thiophenylaldehyde: Condensation with Some Reactive Methylene Compounds

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2-Thiophenylaldehyde has been condensed with malonic, malonanilic, and malon-*o*-, -*m*- and -*p*-toluidic acids using a trace of an organic base like pyridine or piperidine or an equimolar amount of glacial acetic acid as condensing agent; the products obtained have been identified.

The application of the "trace base method" of Pandya and coworkers (*this Journal*, 1934, **9**, 825; *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1935, **2A**, 402) to condensations of various aldehydes including furfuraldehyde and aliphatic aldehydes with malonic acid (George, Ph.D. thesis, Agra University, 1954) revealed a decrease in reactivity with decrease in "aromaticity" of the aldehyde. So it appeared interesting to investigate the behaviour of 2-thiophenylaldehyde, which closely resembles aromatic aldehydes (Bidermann, *Ber.*, 1886, **19**, 639; Dunn and Dittmar, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 2561). This method gives much better yield than the other methods used by earlier workers (Bidermann, *Ber.*, 1886, **19**, 1855; Barger and Eason, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 2100., King and Nord, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1949, **14**, 405; 1950, **15**, 988).

In such condensations 2-thiophenylaldehyde would appear to be slightly less reactive than benzaldehyde, since in the former the carbonyl group is linked to the high electron density centre (Fieser and Fieser, "Organic Chemistry", 2nd ed., 1950, p. 852) as contrast to the electron-accepting phenyl group in the latter. But the present investigation reveals that the reaction goes much faster than that with benzaldehyde (Pandya and Miss Pandya, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1941, **14A**, 112) under the same experimental conditions. The effect of substituents on benzaldehyde in condensation with malonic acid, reported by Pandya and Vahidy (*ibid.*, 1936, **4A**, 140), also reveals that the same type of 'anomalous behaviour', viz., a methoxy substituent, which would make the phenyl group an electron donor, appears to have a favourable influence on the condensation. These observations are apparently contradictory to the current accepted mechanism of Perkin's reaction, viz., an electrophilic attack by the carbonyl carbon atom on the active methylene group.

When 2-thiophenylaldehyde is condensed with malonic acid in presence of traces of pyridine or even piperidine, the non-decarboxylated product (2-thienylmalonic acid) is obtained.

Condensations of the above aldehyde with malonanilic and malon-toluidic acids give the decarboxylated products in presence of piperidine as the catalyst though not with pyridine.

2-Thenalmalonic acid and 2-thenalmalonanilic acid were decarboxylated by gently refluxing with a mixture of pyridine and piperidine to afford 2-thienylacrylic acid and 2-thienylacrylanilide respectively. α - β -Dibromo-2-thenalmalonic acid was prepared by direct addition of bromine to 2-thenalmalonic acid.

A study on the efficiency of pyridine, piperidine, 2,4-lutidine, and glacial acetic acid as condensing agents shows that they exert a catalytic effect, though one cannot say that one has greater effect than the other in all the reactions. Thus lutidine, a good condensing agent in condensations with malonic acid, is found to be not so efficient with malonanilic or malon-toluidic acids. Again glacial acetic acid, which is a poor condensing agent for the former, furnishes almost quantitative yields in the latter cases.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Thenalmalonic Acid—(a). A mixture of 2-thiophenylaldehyde (1.1 g.), malonic acid (1.0 g.), and pyridine (0.1 c.c.) was heated in a small flask at 100° for 40 minutes. The mixture first melted to a light green liquid, but it soon solidified. After cooling this was extracted with a strong solution of sodium bicarbonate. The whole mass dissolved in the alkali solution. It was then washed with ether and the aqueous layer on acidification gave a white precipitate, which on purification by recrystallisation from ethanol yielded 1.4g. (74%) of 2-thenalmalonic acid, m.p. 206° (decomp.). It is sparingly soluble in water in the cold but dissolves readily in hot water and in ethanol. (Found: S, 15.85; equiv., 99. Calc. for $C_8H_6O_4S$: S, 16.16%; equiv., 99).

(b). In a subsequent experiment the yield of 2-thenalmalonic acid rose to 98% when the reaction mixture, prepared as above, was kept at room temperature for an hour prior to heating at 100° for 40 minutes. Piperidine and lutidine in traces as well as an equimolar amount of glacial acetic acid were also used as condensing agents in place of pyridine. The results obtained are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Catalyst.	Time of heating.	Temperature.	Yield %.
Nil	24 hrs.	Room temp.	3.4
"	1	100°	52.0
Pyridine	24	Room temp.	48.0
"	1	100°	90.0
"	40 mins.	"	98.0 (b)
Piperidine	30	"	76.0
2,4-Lutidine .	30	"	85.0
Gl. acetic acid	1 hr.	"	68.0

2-Thienylacrylic Acid.—A mixture of 2-thenalmalonic acid (1 g.), pyridine (4 c.c.), and piperidine (4 drops) was gently refluxed for 30 minutes, cooled, and treated with

excess of HCl (conc.). The precipitated material was filtered, dissolved in sodium bicarbonate solution, and reprecipitated by acid. It was further purified by recrystallisation from ethanol when 0.66g. (85%) of 2-thienylacrylic acid, m.p. 144°, was obtained. (Found: S, 20.70; equiv., 154.4. Calc. for $C_7H_6O_2S$: S, 20.77%; equiv., 154.0).

α - β -Dibromo-2-thienalmalonic Acid.—Bromine (4 g.) in glacial acetic acid (5 c.c.) was added slowly with shaking to a solution of 2-thienalmalonic acid (1 g.) in hot glacial acetic acid (30 c.c.). The flask was then loosely corked and set aside for 5 days. A dark brown solid separating was filtered. A further crop of the same material was obtained on diluting the filtrate with water. These were then recrystallised from ethanol to yield 1.2 g. of α - β -dibromo-2-thienalmalonic acid, m.p. 225°. (Found: S, 9.18. Calc. for $C_8H_6O_4Br_2S$: S, 8.94%).

2-Thienalmalonanilic acid (m.p. 212°) was obtained in 87% yield from malonanilic acid by the same procedure as with 2-thienalmalonic acid, the time of heating being 4 hours. 10% NaOH solution was used for extracting the reaction product as it was insoluble in sodium bicarbonate solution. (Found: S, 11.70; equiv., 273.1. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{11}O_5NS$: S, 11.72%; equiv., 273).

2-Thienylacrylanilide.—Repetition of the above experiment, using a trace of piperidine in place of pyridine as the condensing agent, gave 2-thienylacrylanilide, m.p. 148°. (Found: S, 14.26. Calc. for $C_{13}H_{11}ONS$: S, 13.97%). It was also prepared by decarboxylating 2-thienalmalonanilic acid by refluxing the latter with an excess of pyridine containing a few drops of piperidine; yield 97.5%.

TABLE II

Yields of the products obtained in the condensation with malonanilic acid and malon-*o*-, *m*- and *p*-toluidic acids.

Catalyst.	Malonanilic acid.		Malon- <i>o</i> -toluidic acid.		Malon- <i>m</i> -toluidic acid.		Malon- <i>p</i> -toluidic acid.	
	%Yield.		%Yield.		%Yield.		%Yield.	
	2-Thenal-X.	2-Thenyl-Y.	2-Thenal-X.	2-Thenyl-Y.	2-Thenal-X.	2-Thenyl-Y.	2-Thenal-X.	2-Thenyl-Y.
Nil	64	..	78	..	63	..	70	..
Pyridine	87	..	94	..	51	..	94	..
2,4-Lutidine	62	..	66	..	59	..	70	..
Piperidine	..	98	..	100	3	93	..	99
Gl. acetic acid	100	..	100	..	90	..	100	..

X stands for-malonanilic or -malontoluidic acid.

Y stands for acrylanilide or -acryltoluidide.

*Condensation with Malon-*c*-, *m*- and *p*-toluidic Acids.*—The procedure for these condensations was the same as that described for malonanilic acid. The following products were isolated:

2-Thenalmalon-*o*-toluidic acid, m.p. 216°. (Found: S, 11.48. equiv. 286, $C_{15}H_{13}O_5NS$ requires S, 11.2%, equiv. 287.)

2-Thienylacryl-*o*-toluidide, m.p. 142°. (Found: S, 12.9. $C_{14}H_{13}ONS$ requires S, 13.12%).

2-Thienylmalon-*m*-toluidic acid, m.p. 187°. (Found: S, 11.38. equiv. 286.5; $C_{15}H_{13}O_3NS$ requires S, 11.2%, equiv. 287).

2-Thienylacryl-*m*-toluidide, m.p. 138°. (Found: S, 12.8. $C_{14}H_{13}ONS$ requires S, 13.1%).

2-Thienylmalon-*p*-toluidic acid, m.p. 222°. (Found: S, 11.3, equiv. 286.8; $C_{15}H_{13}O_3NS$ requires S, 11.2%, equiv. 287).

2-Thienylacryl-*p*-toluidide, m.p. 138°. (Found: S, 12.98. $C_{14}H_{13}ONS$ requires S, 13.1%, equiv. 287).

Yields obtained with various condensing agents used are shown in Table II.

The authors are very grateful to the Scientific Research Committee, Uttar Pradesh, for a research grant.